

Housing Cooperatives and India's Housing Needs: Mission Sahkar se Ghar

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Abstract

Prior to the invention of homes, early people lived in natural shelters. Since they frequently moved in search of food sources like plants and animals, they created mobile shelters like tents. The Stone Age was a time when basic necessities and the natural world were essential for survival. One of the most fundamental human requirements, after clothes and food, is housing. A clean, well-maintained home with pleasant surroundings improves the lives of its occupants. A standard housing does not mean merely land and building but includes basic service like water supply, sanitation and access roads. A Cooperative is a voluntary association of individuals united to meet their common economic, social, or cultural needs through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise. It is a sustainable method of meeting the housing requirements of a wide range of people. "A Housing Cooperative is a cooperative society formed to provide its members with dwelling units at fair and reasonable prices, eliminating profit motives and ensuring mutual benefit and welfare of the members." The Research study has been undertaken with the purpose to conceptualize the role of Housing Cooperatives in Sustainable Development of Members of Housing Cooperatives and to highlight the role of Ministry of Cooperation in the allocation of Affordable, Secure and Well maintained Housing facilities in India. The Methodology of this research is an outcome of exploratory research design considering secondary data sources viz., journals, magazines, articles and media reports. The Limitation of the research study is restricted only to descriptive research approach. The Practical Implication of the study is to provide Affordable, Secure and Well maintained Houses for Members focusing on one of the principles given by ICA "Concern for Community". This paper also considering the various Government initiatives under Ministry of Cooperation for Sustainable Development of Housing Cooperatives which focusing on people-centric approach for the development of housing facilities.

Keywords

Cooperatives, Housing Cooperatives, Affordable Housing, Sustainable Development, People-centered approach

Introduction

Cooperative Principle state, "Cooperatives are active in every sector of the global economy".

Housing Cooperatives is one of the eight sectoral organization of the International Cooperative Alliance (ICA). They promote both an economic and social solution to the global shelter crisis. Housing Cooperative is a legal entity typically a cooperative that owns residential property. It operates under regional or national Cooperative laws and stands apart as the only business model with an internationally recognized definition. Housing Cooperatives operate for the benefit of their members, guided by principles like individual responsibility, mutual aid, democracy, equality, and solidarity. They are also committed to transparency and ethical conduct. In essence, they are member-owned and member-run, fostering a community-focused living environment. The power of Housing Cooperatives comes in creating vibrant, democratic communities where people live side by side and work together. They are run by and for their resident members, not for profit. This variety illustrates how cooperative housing can be used in a variety of contexts. Although cooperative models differ by country, they all share a core purpose to meet the economic, social, and cultural needs of their members through community-oriented living. In addition to housing and shelter, Housing Cooperative offers a way to deliver other essential services to the community, such as transportation, education, health care, recreation, and environmental services. Another area where Housing Cooperatives gives impoverished people a chance to be involved in decision-making with their family and community is in the promotion of employment opportunities, project maintenance, and the creation of various social and economic activities for community members. In India, the idea of Housing Cooperatives was introduced by the British who founded the first Cooperative

Societies Act in 1904 but only applied to credit societies for farmers. The first Cooperative Housing Society was set up in the year 1906 in the Mysore State (Now Karnataka) and was known as the Bangalore Building Cooperative Society. Bombay state (Now Maharashtra) also took initiative in this field by forming a non-official Cooperative body in the year 1913. This was known as the Bombay Cooperative Housing Society. The Association did make some pioneering efforts in carrying out propoganda by publishing brochure on various aspects of the Society. It framed a set of nodal Bye-laws which later became the guiding factor for the organization of several other primary Cooperatives. It was also the first to bring in Governmental participation in financial affairs of Housing Co-operatives. (Hajela, T. N. (2016). Cooperation: Principles, Problems and Practice (8th ed.) However, until the 1950s, the growth of housing cooperatives remained limited, mostly because of an unsupportive legislative and administrative environment and an insufficient organisational support structure. In the previous states of Madras and Bombay, efforts were made to build accommodation for middle-class and lower-class individuals. For instance, 273 housing cooperatives in the State of Madras constructed roughly 4,000 homes and another 12,000 were under construction in 1950, while 315 housing cooperatives in the State of Bombay constructed 3,500 homes, including 229 under development. Two events in 1988 changed the face of Indian Housing Policy. Firstly, the National Commission on Urbanisation inferred that housing should, from then on, not restrict itself to the aim of providing shelter, it should explore the broader context of urban development. Secondly, the United Nations Centre for Human Settlements (UNCHS) steered Governments to adopt an "enabling approach" towards housing, by supporting the role of the private and third sectors in housing instead of direct public intervention. Consequently, India along with its states removed legislative barriers to facilitate the participation of the sectors. Since, then Cooperative Housing has grown from strength to strength and presently there are about 1,93,836 Housing Cooperatives out of which 1,77,485 urban Housing Cooperatives societies and 16,351 rural Housing Cooperative societies. (<https://cooperatives.gov.in/en/#>)

Objective of study

The primary objective of the research study is to conceptualize the framework of Housing Cooperatives in India and it also highlights the role of Cooperatives for contributing towards the wellbeing of wider community. The research study also summarizes the essential linkages between Cooperative Principles and Sustainable development of Housing Cooperatives in India. Furthermore, research paper also highlights the key linkage between Housing Cooperatives and affordable, secure, well-maintained and sustainable housing facilities in India.

Scope of the study:

The major scope of the Research study is to describe the growth, structure and role of Housing Cooperatives in India. The study also covering the gap between the India's Housing demand and facilities made accessible and available for the Housing by the Ministry of Housing and Urban affairs, Ministry of Rural Development and Ministry of Cooperation under the Government of India.

Research Approach:

The present study will adopt a descriptive research approach, as it seeks to provide a detailed understanding of how Housing Cooperatives contribute to meeting India's growing housing needs. As the study is in a descriptive nature which also highlights the specific challenges and major solutions for improving the conditions of Housing Cooperatives in India.

Review of Literature

Leeladevi (2014) concluded that housing provision was an integral component of nation-building. She argued that housing cooperatives could sincerely strive to strengthen the primaries at the grassroots level by providing basic and standard facilities required by a common person, such as water, electricity, and sanitary services. Leeladevi also stated that the country's economic and infrastructural development plan could be well supported by having committed leadership within cooperatives.

Tiwari, M., & Ahirwar, G. S. (2017) highlighted recent developments in Swiss housing policy in five large cities and the counter-reactions that emerged due to an acute housing shortage. Their results showed that housing cooperatives were the housing support mechanism that the entire political spectrum could agree on. As the vast majority of cooperatives were non-profit, the authors observed the puzzling situation where neoliberal processes of state withdrawal in social policies led to the promotion of a form of housing that was mostly common property-based.

Keskar, Y. M., Choudhury, B., & Mandal, N. R. (2018) focused on various issues and challenges within the Indian housing market and the affordable housing segment. Their research was preceded by a study of various definitions of affordable housing, housing finance in India, and various initiatives taken by the Government of India through its five-year plans. They concluded that various efforts were required for the development of affordable housing through a multipronged strategy.

Adabre, M. A., & Chan, A. P. (2019) conducted to gather the views of affordable housing experts who were also knowledgeable in sustainable housing from around the world. The purpose was to identify the critical success factors (CSFs) for sustainable affordable housing.

Adabre, M. A., Chan, A. P., & Darko, A. (2022) investigated the causal relationships among 'institutional,' 'economic,' 'social,' and 'environmental' sustainability barriers. They also assessed the effects of these barriers on sustainable housing. Their research revealed that the institutional barriers were causal barriers that had multiplier effects on the economic, social, and environmental barriers. The findings of this study contributed to the global body of knowledge on housing by investigating the interactive effects of these sustainability barriers on sustainable housing.

Methodology

The research paper is an attempt at exploratory research based on secondary data. The required secondary data for completing the investigation will be collected mainly from published sources in Journals, Articles, Books, Web, Government report, National Cooperative Database, etc. An attempt has been made to understand the various initiatives taken by Ministry of Cooperation for Sustainable Development of Housing Cooperatives in India.

Analysis

Concept of Housing Cooperatives:

A Housing Cooperative is a type of Housing owned and managed collectively by its members. Members purchase shares in the cooperative society rather than individual units, which entitles them to live in a housing unit and take part in decision-making. "A Housing Cooperative is a cooperative society formed to provide its members with dwelling units at fair and reasonable prices, eliminating profits motives and ensuring mutual benefit and welfare of the members." (Hajela, T. N. (2016). Cooperation: Principles, Problems and Practice (8th ed.)

Advantages of Housing Cooperatives:

Affordability: Housing is more accessible and might be less expensive than individual ownership because costs are split among participants. Additionally, the costs of upkeep and repairs are divided, reducing the financial burden on any one individual. (<https://www.ica.coop/>)

Access to amenities: Community halls, playgrounds, and sports facilities are examples of amenities that are frequently included in cooperative housing but may not be present in private residences. Residents' or members' quality of life is improved by these facilities.

Achieving Sustainable Development Goal: One important way to provide low- and middle-income people with affordable housing that supports the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is through cooperatives.

Their members' quality of life can be improved by providing employment possibilities and concentrating primarily on community and member participation. (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal11>)

Awareness of community: Living in a cooperative encourages cooperation, trust, and strong social ties among members since homes are planned, designed, and built in accordance with accepted norms and the community.

Financial benefits: Cooperatives are able to provide members with affordable housing while also eliminating the profit margins of middlemen or speculators by obtaining government subsidies, tax exemptions, and low-interest loans.

Figure No. 1.0 Types of Housing Cooperatives:

Source: Hajela, T. N. (2016). Cooperation: Principles, Problems and Practice

Building workers: Societies organized by building workers for the purpose of building houses for sale in the housing market. In this type of society all member directly participates through their personal labour. It is a very simple and practical form of organization which is useful in dealing with housing problem in area mainly rural or small towns.

House Mortgage: Societies specializing in supplying loans to finance house- building. These are in fact, housing credit cooperatives. These are also known as House Mortgage societies. They make available necessary loan facilities to their members. These societies have been organized mostly in the state of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and the Vidarbha area of Maharashtra state.

Tenant Ownership: Societies established to acquire sites for members' future homes. These societies are also known as tenant-ownership housing societies. They help their members in the preparation of site, and financial and technical matter. In these societies the land is sufficiently available and separate houses for each member to suit his choice and liking can be constructed.

Tenant co-partnership: These Cooperatives assign dwellings to their members as if they were their own but members can only dispose of the same subject to certain restrictions laid down in the rules in order to prevent possible speculative selling. Cooperative communities of this sort have provided such facilities as electricity, roads, schools, hospitals, sports fields and sewers. These societies are also known as tenant co-partnership type of societies. These are organized in big cities like Mumbai where land prices are prohibitive and it is more convenient to construct multi- storeyed buildings, to overcome the difficulty of getting sufficient land.

Building/constructor cooperative: These are the societies of house builders, such as carpenters, brick-layers, skilled and unskilled workers. They obtain their funds from financial institutions and build houses for sale or for renting.

Figure No. 2.0 Organizational Structure of Housing Cooperatives:

Source: Housing and Residential Structures by John Short, Keith Bassett

National Cooperative Housing Federation of India (NCHF)

The National Cooperative Housing Federation of India (NCHF) is the Nationwide organization of the Indian Cooperative Housing Movement. It was founded in September, 1969 by the apex cooperative housing federations. The basic thrust of its formation was to have an organization at the national level to assume the responsibility of promoting, developing and coordinating the activities of housing cooperatives in the country. In the course of its existence, NCHF has taken a number of measures for the organization and development of housing cooperatives across the country (<https://nchfindia.net/>).

State Apex Cooperative Housing Federations (ACHF)

A State Apex Cooperative Housing Federation (ACHF) is a central financing and coordinating body for housing cooperatives within a state or union territory. It serves as an apex organization, reporting to the National Cooperative Housing Federation of India (NCHF). ACHFs provide loans to affiliated primary housing cooperatives for construction, and some also offer direct loans to individuals. ACHFs act as a central financial agency for the cooperative housing sector in their respective states. (ibid.)

District Cooperative Housing Federations

A District Cooperative Housing Federation is an organization that represents and supports housing cooperatives within a specific geographic district. These federations act as a resource for member societies, providing guidance, advocacy, and services related to housing, management, and other cooperative-related matters. It represents the collective interests of its member housing societies at the district level and sometimes at higher levels of the cooperative structure.

Primary Cooperative Housing Society

A primary cooperative housing society is a type of cooperative society where members pool resources to acquire land, construct housing, and provide housing units for their collective benefit. These societies are formed by individuals with a common need for

housing and are typically registered under the relevant State Cooperative Societies Act. They are governed by democratic principles, with members having equal rights and responsibilities in managing the society's affairs. (<https://mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files>)

Role of Ministry of Cooperation in Promoting Housing Cooperatives:

The Ministry of Cooperation plays a vital role in strengthening housing cooperatives by providing a supportive framework and promoting their development. It focuses on streamlining processes, enhancing transparency, and fostering a cooperative-based economic model. By increasing Housing Cooperatives' effectiveness, accessibility, and inclusivity, the ministry hopes to boost the country's general prosperity. For Cooperatives, particularly Housing Cooperatives, the Ministry offers a specific administrative, legal, and policy framework. It seeks to revitalize the cooperative movement, guaranteeing its expansion and long-term viability. The Ministry works on streamlining processes and procedures to make it easier for Housing Cooperatives to operate and conduct their business. This includes simplifying registration, compliance, and other administrative tasks. The Ministry encourages computerisation and technology to increase housing cooperatives' efficiency and transparency. This may entail putting in place online systems to handle membership, finances, and other tasks. In order to ensure that housing cooperatives serve every aspect of society, particularly those in rural areas, the Ministry places a strong emphasis on inclusive development. It seeks to ensure that everyone, no matter what financial background, can afford and access housing cooperatives. (<https://www.pib.gov.in>)

Government Schemes for Housing Facilities:

Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY):

The Indian government's Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY) program seeks to provide housing for everyone, including in urban and rural areas. Launched in 2015, the program's goal is to create "Housing for All" by 2022. PMAY-U (urban) and PMAY-G (rural) are the two halves of PMAY.

PMAY-Urban 2.0:

Slum dwellers and members of Economically Weaker Sections (EWS), Low-Income Groups (LIG), and Middle-Income Groups (MIG) are among the urban dwellers for whom housing is intended. (<https://pmay-urban.gov.in/about>)

Credit Linked Subsidy Scheme (CLSS):

Provides interest subsidies on home loans for eligible beneficiaries, including those in the MIG category. (ibid)

PMAY-Gramin:

Aims to supply pucca homes with essential utilities to rural families by 2024. seeks to meet the needs of people living in run-down homes and homeless households.

Awaas Soft and Awaas App are used in an end-to-end e-governance architecture for implementation. Financial aid is sent straight to the beneficiaries' bank accounts. (<https://rural.gov.in/>)

Sardar Patel Awas Yojana (Gujarat):

provides qualified Gujarati recipients financial support for the building of homes. executed by the Gujarat Rural Housing Corporation (GRHC) in rural regions and the Gujarat Housing Board (GHB) and Gujarat Urban Development Mission (GUDM) in urban areas. intends to give impoverished groups in society their own homes in order to raise their standard of existence. (<https://www.myscheme.gov.in/schemes/spay>)

Figure No. 3.0 Key linkages between various Ministry of Government of India and Affordable, Secure and Well-maintained Sustainable Housing Facilities in India:

Source: Developed from Review of Literature

The above given Figure No. 3.0 shows that conceptual framework of housing which give clear idea about the housing facilities provided by various Ministry which are run and operate by Government of India. The Ministry of Cooperation provides a separate legal entity for the housing sector, popularly known as a Housing Cooperative. These cooperatives provide affordable and secure shelter to the community. The Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs provides "pucca" (permanent) houses to urban residents through the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (Urban) or PMAY(U) 2.0. In parallel, the Ministry of Rural Development oversees the PMAY scheme for the rural sector, aiming for affordable "Housing for All." The model also indicates that the Ministry of Finance offers financial assistance for constructing, purchasing, or renting a house through the National Housing Bank (NHB) and the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD). These institutions provide direct loans and grants for rural housing construction and renovation.

The collaboration of these four Ministries Cooperation, Housing and Urban Affairs, Rural Development, and Finance will enable a "Whole of Government" approach. By aligning their initiatives, they can provide affordable, secure, and well-maintained sustainable housing facilities to members of Housing Cooperative Societies, thereby upholding the cooperative's seventh principle, "Concern for the Community." This linkage will ultimately help in the sustainable development of Housing Cooperative Societies.

Figure No. 4.0 Key linkages between Principles of Cooperation and Sustainable Development of Housing Cooperatives in India for Affordable, Secure and Well maintained Housing facilities for Members:

Source: Developed from Review of Literature

The above given Figure No. 4.0 shows that Cooperatives are voluntary organizations open to all individuals who can use their services and accept the responsibilities of membership without any discrimination. As democratic organizations, they're controlled by their members, who have equal voting rights under the "one member, one vote" principle. Members contribute equitably to the capital, and any surplus is allocated to construct dwellings or benefit members in proportion to their transactions with the cooperative. Housing cooperatives are autonomous, allowing them to collaborate with other organizations, including governments, and secure external capital. They focus on educating and training members to ensure the provision of affordable, secure, and well-maintained housing, while also teaching members about their rights and how to utilize cooperative facilities.

Through a member-centric approach, these cooperatives work together across local, regional, national, and international structures to strengthen the cooperative movement and promote the sustainable development of their communities through member-approved policies.

Figure No. 5.0 Role of Government Initiatives and Research Centre for Sustainable and Affordable Housing Facilities:

Source: Developed from Review of Literature

The above given Figure No. 5.0 shows that the "Whole of Government" approach for sustainable and affordable housing is illustrated. This framework shows how various initiatives and entities can contribute to achieving "Vision Viksit Bharat @ 2047". The chart highlights that Government Initiatives, such as the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana - Rural and Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana - Urban 2.0, are central to this effort. It also emphasizes the important role of Housing Cooperative Societies in delivering housing. Simultaneously, a Research Centre is proposed to analyse critical factors like housing demand, affordability, and supply gaps. The collaboration of these elements government schemes, cooperatives, and data-driven research will facilitate Global Collaboration, Policy Support, and Research Opportunities.

Ultimately, these combined efforts aim to achieve Sustainable and Affordable Housing, with the motto "सहकार से घर" (Home through Cooperation), leading to the realization of the larger national vision

Result and Discussion

In order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the perception, behavioural and intentions towards Housing Cooperative societies in India. It may be beneficial for future researcher to conduct studies on above given areas. Further, researcher should prioritize systematically compare the financial models, capital mobilization strategies, and cost structures of a sample of successful, functional Housing Cooperative societies.

Conclusion

As an essential component of stability, security, and well-being, housing is crucial for people, families, and communities. It is more than simply a building; it is an important component of social, economic, and environmental development that affects health, well-being, and even financial success. Cooperative housing not only provide all of these but also provide a sense of ownership to the members of Housing Cooperative societies. Housing Cooperatives is one of the eight sectoral cooperative which not only provide all of these but also provide a sense of ownership to the members of Housing Cooperative societies. Through the whole of Government approach and the various Government schemes such as PMAY(U) for urban people and PMAY(R) for rural sector the Housing

Cooperatives are leading towards the Sustainable Development of housing facilities for serving the needs of the members of Housing Cooperatives. Housing Cooperative with Affordable, Secure, Well-maintained and Sustainable Housing facilities in India which leads to Concern for members of Housing Cooperatives. The facilitating access of financial services of NABARD and National Housing Bank resolved the problems of finance for Housing facilities. Government of India is taking an initiative to facilitate the housing to those without the pucca house with affordable, secure and peaceful surroundings through Housing Cooperatives which leads to concern for the members of Housing Cooperatives.

Suggestions for the future Study

The followings are the recommendation and suggestion of the research study: It is suggested that the collaboration with the various Government bodies and Housing Cooperative Societies make remarkable progress in the area of Housing Cooperative Sector. It is suggested that the suggestion box and complain box may be offered due to the conflict between the members who are residing in the Housing Cooperative Societies. It is suggested that the Housing Cooperative Societies Awareness Campaign to make aware people about the "Sahkar se Ghar". It is suggested that the local leaders of Rural, Taluka and District level must provide basic knowledge of Cooperative Principles to the overall communities.

Limitation of the Study

The data is collected from secondary sources so the data may operationalize or conceptualize differently than primary researcher. The information and data may not be accurate as it is based on secondary data. The secondary data that are suitable for one enquiry may not necessarily be found suitable in another enquiry. Hence, if the available data are found to be unsuitable, they should not be used by researcher. The data will also be considered inadequate, if they are related to an area which may be either narrower or wider than the area of present enquiry.

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